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C. 1. 1.

Evelix Cottage
Evelix,
Donnoch,
Sutherland

29. 11. 71.

Dear Andrew,

Thank you for your
letter. I am glad to hear
about the pottery shipment.
Well done.

Chishman's address is:

96 rue La Fontaine, Paris 16e.

I expect he is there at this
time.

I shall be lecturing on
Nush-i-jan at the Schoolhouse
on Dec. 16th at 3 p.m. if you

should still be about Oxford
at that time.

Michael reports the roof
damage fully repaired;
apparently the temple
itself was all right.

Hope to see you possibly
at Oxford.

Yours,

Daniel,